

Formal Record of *Mecopus hopei* Rosenschöld, 1838 (Curculionidae: Conoderinae) in Taiwan

WEI-ZHE TSENG^{1, 2}, REN-CHUNG CHENG^{2, 3}

¹ Department of Life Science, National Taiwan Normal University, No. 88, Sec. 4, Tingzhou Rd., Taipei City 116059, Taiwan. E-mail: jay584371@gmail.com

² Department of Life Sciences, National Chung Hsing University

³ Research Center for Global Change Biology, National Chung Hsing University
No. 145 Xingda Rd., South Dist., Taichung 40227, Taiwan.

Abstract: *Mecopus hopei* Rosenschöld, 1838 is a common species in Taiwan. However, it has been frequently misspelled in Taiwanese records, leading to its omission from regional catalogs. In this study, we formally record *M. hopei* in Taiwan and provide dorsal habitus photos and barcode sequences to improve species identification.

Keywords: Mecopini, jackfruit bud weevil, pest, DNA barcode

The first record of *Mecopus hopei* Rosenschöld, 1838 in Taiwan dates back to a 1999 report by the Taitung District Agricultural Improvement Station (1999). This report mentioned the species as a jackfruit pest but lacked details and misspelled its name. This misspelling became widely used in pest management research (e.g., Hsien, 2001), resulting in its exclusion from the Palaearctic Coleoptera catalogue (Alonso-Zarazaga et al., 2017; Shao, 2020). This study formally documents *M. hopei* in Taiwan, providing dorsal habitus photos from the holotype and Taiwanese population, along with barcode sequences to aid species identification.

Specimens were examined and photographed using an SMZ 800D stereomicroscope with SGviews software (Sage Vision CO., Ltd., Taiwan). Cytochrome c oxidase subunit I (barcode region) sequences were amplified following Tseng & Cheng (2021) method. Deposits of the specimens can be found at the National Museum of Natural Science, Taichung, Taiwan (NMNS), and the Oxford University Museum of Natural History (OUMNH).

Mecopus hopei Rosenschöld, 1838

霍氏大眼象鼻蟲、波羅蜜象鼻蟲

(Figure 1)

Type material examined. Holotype: 1♂, “blank” [black rectangular label] / Hope [black rectangular label] / Bengal [white rectangular label] / *Mecopus hopei* [white rectangular label] / COL: 1492 (OUMNH).

Material examined. TAIWAN: 2♂♂, Taipei Municipal Chung-Cheng Senior High School (臺北市立中正高中), Shilin District, Taipei City, 8. III. 2020, W.-Z. Tseng leg. // WZPCC_01980 – WZPCC_01981 (NMNS); 1♂1♀, Taichung Municipal Chang-Yi Senior High School (臺中市立長億高中), Taiping District, Taichung City, N24.11373 E120.72119, 22. XI. 2021, P.-S. Lee & W.-Z. Tseng leg. // WZPCC_03633 – WZPCC_03634 (NMNS).

GenBank accession number. WZPCC_01980: OR515184; WZPCC_01981: OR515231; WZPCC_03633: OR515230; WZPCC_03634: OR515229

Remarks. This species is a major pest of *Artocarpus heterophyllus* Lam. in Taiwan (Taitung District Agricultural Improvement Station, 1999; Hsien, 2001). It is also found on the trunks of *Ficus microcarpa* L.F. and *Bombax ceiba* L. However, its scientific name is often misspelled as 'Mecopus nose' in Taiwanese records (e.g., Hsien, 2001).

The authors acknowledge the Genomics Center for Clinical and Biotechnological Applications of the National Core Facility for Biopharmaceuticals, Taiwan (MOST 109-2740-B-010-002), Dr. Amoret Spooner (OUMNH) for providing detailed photos of

the holotype specimen, Mr. Pei-Shiuan Li for fieldwork assistance, and the valuable comments of the reviewers and the proofreading by the TJES English editor.

Figure 1. Dorsal habitus of *Mecopus hopei* Rosenschöld, 1838. A: Taiwanese population, B: holotype.

References

- Alonso-Zarazaga, M. A., Barrios, H., Borovec, R., Bouchard, P., Caldara, R., Colonnelli, E., Gültekin, L., Hlaváč, P., Korotyaev, B., Lyal, C. H. C., Machado, A., Meregalli, M., Pierotti, H., Ren, L., Sánchez-Ruiz, M., Sforzi, A., Silfverberg, H., Skuhrovec, J., Trýzna, M., Velázquez de Castro, A. J., & Yunakov, N. N. 2017. Cooperative Catalogue of Palaearctic Coleoptera Curculionoidea. Sociedad Entomológica Aragonesa (eds). Monografías electrónicas SEA 8, Zaragoza, Spain. 729 pp.
- Hsien, C.-L. 2001. Occurrence and integrative management of jack fruit weevil. *Bulletin of Taitung District Agricultural Improvement Station* 38: 9–12. (in Chinese)
- Shao, K.-T. 2020. Catalogue of life in Taiwan. Web electronic publication. version 2020. Available at <http://taibnet.sinica.edu.tw> (accessed 29 December 2022).
- Taitung District Agricultural Improvement Station. 1999. Annual Report (1998). Taitung District Agricultural Improvement Station, Taitung, Taiwan. 118 pp. (in Chinese)
- Tseng, W.-Z. & Cheng R.-C. 2021. First record of genus *Phaeopholus* Roelofs, 1873 (Coleoptera: Curculionidae: Hyperinae) in Taiwan. *Taiwanese Journal of Entomological Studies* 6 (2): 6–12.

臺灣產霍氏大眼象鼻蟲之正式紀錄（象鼻蟲科：大眼象鼻蟲亞科）

曾偉哲^{1,2}、鄭任鈞^{2,3}

¹ 國立臺灣師範大學生命科學系 80424 臺北市文山區汀洲路四段 88 號

² 國立中興大學生命科學系

³ 國立中興大學生命科學院全球變遷生物學研究中心 40227 臺中市南區興大路145號

摘要：霍氏大眼象鼻蟲是臺灣的常見物種，然而臺灣的紀錄經常錯誤拼寫本種的學名，以至於古北界鞘翅目名錄並未收錄本種臺灣的分布紀錄。本文提供臺灣產霍氏大眼象鼻蟲的正式紀錄，並附上標本背面照與生命條碼序列以利物種鑑定。

關鍵字：大眼象鼻蟲族、波羅蜜象鼻蟲、害蟲、生命條碼